

«USING INTERNET IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS»

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The expediency of using new information technologies is dictated by the needs of modern education to increase the effectiveness of learning, in particular, the need to develop skills for independent learning, search activities, a creative approach to learning, the formation of critical thinking in modern schoolchildren [2]. The use of Internet technologies in teaching a foreign language is conditioned not only by the desire to modernize the learning process, but also by the fact that on the basis of web technologies it becomes possible to implement a personality-oriented approach both to the student and to the entire learning process as a whole, which is the main direction of education in our time [1].

Various resources appear every day to help you learn English. With the help of some Internet resources, it is even possible to independently study the language.

1. Learning English [3].

This resource has a simple interface, it will be convenient for a child who is just beginning to master the basics of the English language. A teacher can easily teach the English alphabet using the exercises on this resource. The name of each letter is voiced and written in Russian letters. Here you can learn words by topic. Each word has a translation and sound recording, so ask your child to repeat the words after the speaker. After learning the words, it is proposed to perform several different exercises to consolidate the material. For schoolchildren, the site contains a block of grammar learning. It should be noted that theoretical knowledge and explanations are still lacking. On this resource, you can study vocabulary on a variety of topics: numbers from 1 to 10, colors, fruits, vegetables, family, pets, animals, furniture, professions and many others.

2. Lingvaleo. Course "English for the smallest" [6]. This source is one of the most popular sites on the Internet for learning English, designed for both adults and children. It is based on learning English in a playful way with the help of original materials and exercises. Separately, it is worth highlighting the course "English for the smallest", designed for younger students. There are three blocks of tasks in the course. Learning the alphabet. My family and pets. How do you feel? Classes are held in the form of interactive tasks, where you need to choose the correct answer, match a word and a picture, put words out of letters, etc.

3. Puzzle English - "Teacher's method" [7]. The Teacher Method includes five courses of different difficulty levels, plus a separate "Children's Course". The children's course is aimed at children from 5 years old. The material is presented in the form of stories with the participation of characters: teacher Miss Betty, children Johnny and Kate, Peter the owl.

4. LearnEnglish Kids [4]. On this site you can find materials for children of preschool and primary school age: songs, short stories, videos, games, exercises, etc.

They are all well developed. For example, if you open a video, then it will not be just a page with a video, but a whole set of tasks: first an exercise where you need to match words and a picture, then a video, then a test, and useful pdf files are also attached to the video.

There is this heading on the site:

1. Listen and Watch - videos and exercises for them. Songs are highlighted in a separate sub-heading.
2. Read and Write - short reading texts and simple writing exercises.
3. Speak and Spell - video and text materials, pronunciation exercises (reading rules) and spelling.
4. Grammar and Vocabulary - video lessons, exercises and games on grammar.
5. Fun and Games - mini-games for learning English.
6. Print and Make - materials for printing: vocabulary cards, coloring books, miniworkbooks (worksheets) and others.
7. Parents - a section for parents with articles, useful tips on how to help children learn English. This section includes video tutorials where teachers explain how to play educational games with young children.
8. Starfall Education [8].

This resource is considered fairly easy to use. Here you can find exercises for learning the alphabet, reading rules, short tests with pictures. Each word is voiced, you can listen to it. Kids will love the colorful design, interesting stories to read, and large, well-written letters. Many new words and sentences are remembered thanks to the games.

9. Cambridge English Online [5]. A separate service with rich content was invented for children: games, cognitive tasks, thematic flash cards, songs, stories. However, the site navigation is poor, it will take a long time to sort out the confusing navigation in English. Also, on the site you can download various teaching materials in English, which can be printed on a printer and practiced without the help of a computer. The article reviewed the resources that are most

convenient to use during a foreign language lesson. It is worth noting that all these Internet resources are aimed at a modernized level of education, the implementation of new teaching methods, as well as the formation of not only subject skills, but also the ability to work with information and communication technologies. But in our opinion, it is impossible to sufficiently master the skill of speaking with the help of Internet resources, therefore, it is not worth replacing traditional teaching methods with Internet technologies. You should use Internet resources in conjunction with traditional methods.

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